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Innovative Climate-Control System to Extend Range of Electric Vehicles and Improve Comfort (XERIC)

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Report:

XERIC’s 2nd Newsletter

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Summary:

This is the second of XERIC’s e-newsletters. The e-newsletters are released twice a year. This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created and sent and what makes up the mailing lists.

The newsletter is then displayed.

The appendices display the documents that open when one clicks on the links in the online version of the newsletter.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
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1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to the *WordPress* Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically as emails. The software splits the mailing list and doesn't send the e-newsletter to more than 30 persons at a time so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Mailing lists

We created 3 mailing lists in 2015 for the different communication purposes that we may have.

- List 1 : all the persons working for XERIC at XERIC's partners';
- List 2 : other persons at XERIC's partners' it may be nice to inform about XERIC's existence, activities and big annual workshops;
- List 3 : other persons not part of XERIC whom the partners want to be aware of XERIC.

Total : 123 persons.

In May 2016, list 3 was expanded: the current total number of subscribers is **150**.

XERIC's 1st e-newsletter has been sent to all 3 mailing lists (150 persons).

3. Newsletter 1

See next page and appendices for all the links that can be opened when browsing the newsletter online.

Newsletter 2 - May 2016

Editorial by Nino Gaeta

Welcome to the second XERIC newsletter.

XERIC has taken up a stimulating challenge: extending the range of electric vehicles by developing a novel climate control system. We are developing a **hybrid system** based upon an innovative **three-fluids-combined membrane contactor (3F-CMC)** that simultaneously works with air, desiccant solution, and refrigerant.

The first year was very busy: amongst other things, a **novel PVDF membrane** was prepared, a special **plasma treatment** is being developed to further increase its hydrophobicity, a **desiccant** was selected, the **design** of the first prototype of the membrane contactor was completed, its **mechanical stability** was modelled, and **numerical simulations** were carried out. It all resulted in the preparation of the preliminary **3F-CMC prototype!**

(...) Thanks to our newsletters, you'll get to know the expertise of the teams involved in XERIC. For this edition, we're travelling to VITO's plasma group and UDE's 'Technical Chemistry II Chair'. We are also giving you the opportunity to discover the researchers involved in XERIC on an individual basis: in this edition, we're getting a glimpse into the daily life of Stefano Lazzari, Sabine Paulussen and Marta Bojarska. (...)

Nino Gaeta - GVS spa - XERIC's Coordinator

[Read more](#)

Get to know the XERIC researchers - INTERVIEWS

Dr. Stefano LAZZARI

University of Genoa, Italy

Stefano's work falls within the **Industrial Engineering and Environmental Engineering** branches. He brings into XERIC his expertise in **modelling heat transfer** and optimising the performance of heat exchangers.

"[It's] very satisfying when any suggestion of change in the 3F-CMC design turns to be an enhancement in the overall air conditioning system, according to preliminary numerical evaluations. Since some modifications are not easy to be implemented from the manufacturing standpoint, finding the right compromise with the industrial partners is always a great victory!"

[Read the full interview](#)

Dr. Sabine PAULUSSEN

VITO, Belgium

Sabine is part of VITO's plasma technology team. She coordinated a European-funded project and is part of an Initial Training Network.

"Plasma is actually the 4th state of matter, besides the solid, liquid and gas states. It is an ionized gas meaning that the molecules in a gas are further split into, amongst others, radicals, ions and electrons,

by adding energy to the gas. A plasma can be generated by heating, but also for example by applying an electric field, which is what we do in the lab."

[Read the full interview](#)

Dr. Marta BOJARSKA

UDE, Germany

Marta is a postdoc researcher at UDE. Her PhD thesis dealt with hydrogen separation from after-fermentation gases.

"I, along with the rest of the UDE team involved in XERIC, am trying to obtain a lab scale membrane prototype. Basically, we are focusing on a phase separation method and its aspects for

membrane formation. (...) In my opinion the most challenging part of this task is yet to come. It is up-scaling and transfer of membrane production from University to Industry."

[Read the full interview](#)

Poster Award to XERIC PhD student

2nd place for Best Poster Presentation

We are proud to announce that **Clemens Alexowsky**, a XERIC PhD student at the University of Duisburg-Essen in Germany, received the 2nd place for Best Poster Presentation for the poster he presented at the European Young Engineers Conference in April in Warsaw, Poland.

The aim of Clemens's work is to prepare **hydrophobic and highly porous polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membranes** with high porosity and tunable and narrow barrier pore size distribution in the range from ~0.1 to ~1 μm using the **vapor induced phase separation (VIPS) technique**. In the poster, the focus is put on the differences of the None-Solvent Induced Phase Separation and VIPS method as well as the exposure time of the cast film in humid air.

[View the poster](#)

More on the following page.

Discover XERIC partners' expertise

VITO's plasma tech group

The group is made up of 18 staff members working on process and equipment development with a strong focus on **industrial implementation** and transfer of knowledge. VITO's atmospheric plasma technology provides **solutions for sustainable and solvent-free surface treatment**. It allows dedicated

chemical functionalisation of any substrate (plastic, glass, metal).

[Read more](#)

UDE: the Ulbricht's Group - Membranes

Universität Duisburg-Essen (UDE) offers a broad spectrum of fields, with a strong focus on sciences, engineering and medicine. The "Technische Chemie II" Chair (TCII) has a key position within research and teaching in UDE's Chemistry Department. Research carried out by Prof. Ulbricht's group is devoted to **functional polymeric materials** with a focus on

separation membranes and particular emphasis on applications in **water purification** and related processes. Core competences of his group include development of polymer-based membranes, coatings or surface modifications with various functionalities such as hydrophilic or hydrophobic, antifouling and molecular recognition.

[Read more](#)

More on the following page.

One-day event: Improving Energy Efficiency in EVs

Grow your network!

Increasing the **range of electric vehicles** remains one of the biggest challenges in the automotive industry. As a result, XERIC and 2 other EU-funded projects have decided to organise a one-day event on the latest trends and technologies to improve energy efficiency in electric vehicles.

You're from R&D or Industry, or maybe you're an end user? Join us on **November 24** in **Bologna, Italy**:

- you'll learn what the European Commission is doing for electric mobility;
- you'll get a unique insight into the latest research and development on energy management in electric vehicles;
- you'll establish new contacts for collaborations thanks to bilateral meetings that you'll have pre-booked online.

Access to the event is FREE if you register.

Online registration will start in June on a dedicated website: you'll receive an email when registration opens.

If you have any questions or need more information, don't hesitate to get in touch with our Communication Officer, *Guyène Soula*, at guyene.soula@univ-montp2.fr.

www.xeric.eu

4. Appendices

- Editorial by Nino Gaeta, XERIC's coordinator
- 3 interviews (Stefano Lazzari – UNIGE ; Sabine Paulussen – VITO; Marta Bojarska – UDE)
- Poster by Clemens Alexowsky

Welcome to the second XERIC newsletter.

XERIC has taken up a stimulating challenge: extending the range of electric vehicles by developing a novel climate control system. We are developing a hybrid-system based upon an innovative three-fluids-combined membrane contactor (3F-CMC) that simultaneously works with air, desiccant solution, and refrigerant.

The first year was very busy:

amongst other things, a **novel PVDF membrane** was prepared, a **special plasma treatment** is being developed to further increase its hydrophobicity, a **desiccant** was selected, the **design of the first prototype of the membrane contactor** was completed, its mechanical stability was modelled, and numerical simulations were carried out. It all resulted in the **preparation of the preliminary 3F-CMC prototype!**

Especially rewarding for me, as coordinator, was to see the **constant growth of a truly transdisciplinary and collaborative attitude** of all people working within XERIC. Professors, scientists, managers, younger post-doctors and PhD students work synergistically to reach a common objective that could revolutionise the climate control in vehicles and especially in electric ones.

Thanks to our newsletters, you'll **get to know the expertise of the teams** involved in XERIC. For this edition, we're travelling to VITO's plasma group and UDE's 'Technical Chemistry II' Chair. We are also giving you the opportunity to **discover the researchers** involved in XERIC on an individual basis: in this edition, we're getting a glimpse into the daily life of Stefano Lazzari, Sabine Paulussen and Marta Bojarska.

In XERIC, we're also looking for synergy by clustering with other EC-funded projects. The JOSPEL and OPTEMUS projects give us a hand with the organization of our **first joint public event**, so save the date: our 1-day public event devoted to *Improving Energy Efficiency in Electric Vehicles* will take place on **November 24, 2016** in **Bologna, Italy**. You'll get a unique insight into the latest research and development on energy management in electric vehicles, **you'll grow your network** and establish new contacts for collaborations. We hope to see many of you there.

We welcome any comment or suggestion from all people interested in our project and we invite you to read more about it on our website: www.xeric.eu.

Nino Gaeta
GVS SPA
XERIC's Coordinator

Interview with **Stefano LAZZARI**

Researcher at the University of Genoa, Italy
XERIC's Deputy Coordinator

Dr Stefano Lazzari is a researcher in the Department of Architectural Sciences at the University of Genoa, Italy. Stefano's work falls within the Industrial Engineering and Environmental Engineering branches. Stefano brings into XERIC his expertise in modelling heat transfer and optimizing the performance of heat exchangers.

What made you opt for a career as a researcher? How would you define your job?

I would say that I like to study, to face new problems as well as to teach what I have learned. There is no better place to work other than the University if these are your favourite activities! My job is challenging, very dynamic and gives me the chance to see both the perspective of students and that of the companies that ask for consultancy.

We'd like to catch a glimpse of your daily activities. What is a typical day for you?

Since my job is very dynamic, there is no typical day in the strict sense of the word. I can say that usual activity is made of lectures, examinations, meetings, writing of research papers and review of papers submitted for publication on journals and conference by Colleagues from all over the world. Besides this, since I am involved in XERIC as both researcher and Deputy Coordinator, my work consists in both proceeding with the development of the XERIC system towards the final goal and in helping the Coordinator in keeping the teams strictly connected, trying to overcome any issues by having my eye on the project's various tasks and activities. This is why I am used to working hard all day long and often also in the weekend!

Your expertise spans the chemical engineering, industrial engineering and environmental branches. What do you bring to the transdisciplinary XERIC project? And what are you expecting from your participation in XERIC?

The XERIC project is very ambitious and challenging, since it involves many different aspects going from fundamental heat and mass transfer optimization to performance evaluation by means of numerical modeling, from membrane development to product manufacturing, from electronic management of the system to dissemination activities. I am proud of being part of such a transdisciplinary project and I am doing my best in order to help designing the innovative component (called three-fluids membrane contactor, 3F-CMC) and to enhance the performance of the overall air conditioning system.

Having the maximum respect towards the high professionalism and effort provided by all other partners I am growing both from a professional standpoint and from a personal standpoint. Working together is stimulating and, I am confident about this, will give the desired results in the end.

What do you think is the most satisfying part of this project?

We are only in the first year of the project and, thus, the complete answer cannot be given yet. Anyway, the European call for projects itself was highly-demanding and just having been funded is extremely satisfying. Indeed it means that the fundamental idea underneath XERIC is definitely worth the effort.

Personally speaking, I find very satisfying when any suggestion of change in the 3F-CMC design turns to be an enhancement in the overall air conditioning system, according to preliminary numerical evaluations. Since some modifications are not easy to be implemented from the manufacturing standpoint, finding the right compromise with the industrial partners is always a great victory!

And the most frustrating part?

Fortunately, we have not faced yet any unsolvable problem, so the many difficulties we have encountered and overcome are more a satisfying part than a frustrating part of the project!

You've recently participated in HERB, an EU-funded project bringing together 18 EU partners. What was your role in this project?

In the Holistic Energy Efficient Retrofitting of Residential Buildings (HERB) project, the research group of the University of Bologna, where I have been working from 1999 to 2014, was responsible for the optimization of air-water and ground-water heat pumps for air conditioning in residential buildings. Moreover, our group gave the technical and scientific support to the City of Bologna for the realization of the proposed high efficiency energy retrofitting solutions on a building owned by the municipality of Bologna. In detail, I was responsible for the dynamic simulation of the building, aimed at determining the energy performance before and after any energy retrofitting.

XERIC brings together research labs and industry. How do you view research-industry collaborations within the framework of the project? Shifting the focus to a bigger frame, how do you view the future of research: will most research be carried out via public-private collaborations?

Until now, the cooperation between research groups from the University and industrial partners works in a very efficient way. This is probably due to the presence in the consortium of ITWM that, being a pure research center, often acts as a translator between the opposite approaches of Academia and Industry. This is why I feel that this kind of European-funded projects can really help in promoting public-private collaborations in research activities. Especially in this critical moment in the world economy, the industry has an increasing need in shifting outside the risk connected with the investment in research and, on the opposite, the University should not lose the chance to focus its research also on practical commercial problems. Therefore, in my opinion the future will see more patents made by Universities.

Thanks for answering my questions Stefano and all the best for XERIC!

Stefano's skills

Heat Transfer - Fluid Mechanics -
Energy Engineering - Refrigeration & Air
Conditioning – Low enthalpy geothermal
energy - Computational Fluid Dynamics -
Comsol Multiphysics

Role of the University of Genoa (UNIGE) in XERIC

UNIGE in the project acts as Third Party of TICASS (Innovative Technologies for Environmental Control and Sustainable Development), which is a non-profit Consortium based in Italy, in the Liguria region. UNIGE and TICASS work side by side to design and model the 3F-CMC and the overall climate control system.

UNIGE co-invented and patented the three-fluids-combined membrane contactor.

XERIC in brief

XERIC is a European Research & Innovation Project

Start date:
1st June 2015

End date:
31st May 2018

Number of partners: 8

Coordinator:
Dr. Eng. S. GAETA
GVS spa
Italy

Programme:
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European Research & Innovation Project
Innovative climate-control system to extend range of electric vehicles and improve comfort

Interview with **Sabine PAULUSSEN**

Researcher at VITO, Belgium

Dr. Sabine PAULUSSEN joined VITO's plasma technology group in 2001. She is in charge of technology development in the field of multifunctional coatings. Sabine has coordinated several European R&I projects. She brings into XERIC her expertise on plasma technology.

What made you opt for a career as a researcher? How would you define your job?

What I particularly like about research is the chance to do things nobody has ever done before. It brings a certain excitement to wait for the outcome of experiments, or to obtain unexpected results. On the other hand I also like to analyse problems to find a solution or to set up a research proposal out of a specific case, bringing together different research areas to achieve a specific goal. All of this is part of my job at VITO.

We'd like to catch a glimpse of your daily activities. What is a typical day like for you?

My job is very diverse and it is difficult to define a typical day. Sometimes, I spend the whole day in the lab, for example together with customers attending trials. Other days I work in my office writing proposals or reports. Very often we also visit or invite companies to demonstrate and discuss our technology with the aim of setting up collaborations.

VITO developed an innovative plasma technology at normal atmospheric pressure to permanently change the surface of materials. What are plasma and plasma technology? Why is it interesting for industry? Can you give us a sample of industrial applications?

Plasma is actually the 4th state of matter, besides the solid, liquid and gas states. It is an ionized gas meaning that the molecules in a gas are further split into, amongst others, radicals, ions and electrons, by adding energy

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to the gas. A plasma can be generated by heating, but also for example by applying an electric field, which is what we do in the lab. We make use of the energetic species in the plasma to modify the surface of materials, without altering the bulk properties of a material. For example polymer fibers are often rather hydrophobic. By plasma treatment of such fibers, we can improve the strength of composite materials that are produced from the fibers, due to a better compatibility between the fibers and the matrix in which they are embedded. A similar effect could be obtained with wet chemical coatings but materials are often not compatible with water or solvents. From an environmental point of view, plasma technology has a lower environmental footprint than alternative technologies.

You coordinated the NANOPUR European-funded project. This 3-year project ended in 2015. It dealt with nano-structured membranes for water treatment. Has the project achieved its objectives?

The objective of the NANOPUR project was to create membranes for water purification that use less energy than conventional membranes and are capable to combine high flow rates and high retention of micro-pollutants. In a first research path, membrane preparation was optimized in order to achieve a higher flux through the membranes and to make them less susceptible to fouling and easier to clean. In a second track, affinity ligands able to capture pollutants and pathogens were synthesized and immobilized on the membranes.

This way we managed to develop nano-structured membranes that possess a higher permeability than current ultra-filtration (UF) membranes while being capable of removing viruses, endocrine disrupting compounds, antibiotics and bacteria toxins from water. While some of the new developments within NANO-PUR are already being implemented in industrial processes, more research and (cost-) optimization is needed to reach this level for other innovations resulting from the project.

You're participating in RAPID, an Initial Training Network funded by the European Commission. RAPID hired 15 PhD students and postdoc researchers. Can you tell us more about this project?

The RAPID project groups 10 European universities and research institutes renowned for their work in the field of atmospheric plasma technology and 10 companies interested in the technology. The aim is to achieve transfer of knowledge to the industry and penetration of atmospheric plasma technology in industrial processes by educating PhD students on the subject. This is not only achieved by hosting PhDs but also by dedicated training courses for the students involved and by mobility of the students through internships in the different institutes and companies. Atmospheric plasma technology is an interdisciplinary topic at the intersection of chemistry, physics and engineering and the exchange within the group of students and their mentors is very vibrant and motivating.

Let's talk about XERIC now! Why is it interesting for you to participate in XERIC?

We have a very challenging task within XERIC. Our job is to make the new separator membranes that are being developed more hydrophobic by applying a plasma coating. We made hydrophobic coatings for other applications, but for XERIC the stability requirements are much more challenging and already at this stage we learned a lot. I also particularly like the idea that we contribute to a project which is driven by industry, and the outcome of which may have an environmental and societal impact.

XERIC brings together research labs and industry. Given your experience at VITO, which positions itself as an innovation partner for industry, how do you view the future of research: will most research be carried out via public-private collaborations?

From my point of view it is essential to involve industry from the beginning onwards in new application-oriented R&D tracks. This way the relevance of the work is assured and new developments can be tailored towards the needs of the industry, as such being more efficient, not only technologically but also financially.

Thanks for answering my questions Sabine and all the best for XERIC!

Sabine's skills

Plasma - Materials Science - Chemistry
Polymers - Chemical Engineering
Nanotechnology - Technology Transfer
Innovation Management

VITO, a partner in the XERIC project

VITO is the Flanders' research and technology organisation on cleantech and sustainable development. With approximately 750 researchers and supporting staff, VITO is one of the largest European research institutes active in the fields of energy, environment and materials. VITO's plasma technology group is made up of 18 staff members. They work on process and equipment development with a strong focus on industrial implementation and transfer of knowledge.

XERIC in brief

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European Research & Innovation Project
Innovative climate-control system to extend range of electric vehicles and improve comfort

Interview with **Marta BOJARSKA**

Postdoc researcher at the University of Duisburg-Essen

Germany

I came to work in XERIC from Poland. My field of study actually has been changing a little bit over the years. I started with my master degree at Warsaw University of Technology (WUT) in Industrial Biotechnology. The topic of my thesis was related to membrane gas separation; I was focusing on hydrogen separation from after-fermentation gases. Then, I defended my PhD at the Faculty of Chemical and Process Engineering, WUT. In this work I focused on surface modification of commercial membranes.

... And now I am doing my postdoc training at the University of Duisburg Essen (UDE), Faculty of Chemistry. As you can see I have been changing the faculties with every step, but I have been faithful to membranes from the very beginning.

You told me that PhDs in Poland take longer than the average 3 years. Can you briefly explain why? What additional experience did this extra time give you?

Yes, apart from our work focusing on the thesis, we are obliged to have classes with students and attend specialized courses. Apart from this, we work in projects that are not always part of our PhD thesis. For example I was working in three different projects and at the end of my PhD I started to work in small company in R&D section. For sure this extra time gives us an additional experience both in research as well as in teaching. Also during that time I had a chance to cooperate with industry and see their approach to problems and science, I was very fortunate during my PhD studies, because I had many opportunities to develop as a researcher.

What is your postdoc project about? What objectives do you have to reach to contribute to the XERIC project?

I, along with the rest of the UDE team involved in XERIC, am trying to obtain a lab scale membrane prototype. Basically,

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we are focusing on a phase separation method and its aspects for membrane formation. The membranes obtained will work in XERIC's 3FCMC in order to reduce at least 50% of energy used for passenger comfort in electric vehicles. In my opinion the most challenging part of this task is yet to come. It is up-scaling and transfer of membrane production from University to Industry. UDE along with GVS Filter Technology will be closely collaborating in order to achieve this goal within XERIC's 3-year duration.

What is the best thing about undertaking a postdoc? How challenging is it?

Postdoc training gave me a great opportunity to work with Professor Mathias Ulbricht and his group. Also thanks to this project every day I am learning something new and I have an opportunity to cooperate with people from different fields. This is very eye-opening and an illuminating experience. The project and the postdoc give me an opportunity to see how a European Project is structured and how many different aspects it covers; now I know what are the requirements, obligations, responsibilities but also possibilities related with this kind of a project.

You participated in the "European Young Engineers Conference" in Poland in April. This conference brought together an audience of about 90 persons. Your talk was entitled "Membranes in automotive climate control systems". Was it a profitable experience? What did you learn there?

The European Young Engineers Conference is a conference organized by students for students and PhD candidates. This year I was honored and invited as a speaker. Every year they are trying to invite some "fresh" PhD to show others what people can do after the defense. This conference gave me an opportunity to show younger colleagues what my work is about and how does the European Project works. It was a good experience to talk with students involved with research and see their point of view on different topics.

You applied to the LIDER Programme last year and you were one of the lucky – and hard-working- researchers who got funded! This ~300,000 euros grant is meant to help young scientists learn how to plan research on their own, manage and lead their own research team while carrying out projects likely to be implemented on the market. So you're a team leader in Poland. What is your team working on? What are your impressions on managing a group of persons?

Yes, the LIDER project is dedicated to researchers under 35 years of age and last year there was really great competition. Me and my team are working on polypropylene filters modification. We are modifying filters with aerogels in order to enhance water/oil and air/oil separation.

Already when I was writing a proposal I had an entire team ready, also we have started to talk with one of the Polish companies that is interested in our idea. Managing a group of persons is not an easy task, but I am a lucky team leader. My team consists of very good specialists and some very promising young researchers. Also we all know and like each other, which helps a great deal.

On a more general note, what is appealing to you in being a researcher?

When you are a scientist you work all the time, not only in office or laboratory but also during morning teeth brushing or car ride (in my case tram); you think how to solve problems or why doesn't it work the way I want it to work. Science is challenging but also very rewarding. Every day there is something new to discover. Even when I am stuck with research, which happens occasionally, there is always an alternative route. And when you finally are able to solve a problem you feel just great! Being a scientist/researcher gives me a little bit of freedom for working out creative ideas.

**Thanks for answering my questions
Marta and all the best for your projects!**

UDE, a partner in the XERIC project

Universität Duisburg-Essen (UDE) offers a broad spectrum of fields, with a strong focus on sciences, engineering and medicine. The "Technische Chemie II" Chair (TCII) has a key position within research and teaching in UDE's Chemistry Department. Research carried out by Prof. Ulbricht's group is devoted to functional polymeric materials with a focus on separation membranes and particular emphasis on applications in water purification and related processes. Core competences of his group include development of polymer-based membranes or surface modifications with various functionalities such as hydrophilic or hydrophobic, antifouling and molecular recognition.

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Preparation of macroporous hydrophobic flat-sheet PVDF membranes via vapor induced phase separation

Clemens Alexowsky, Marta Bojarska and Mathias Ulbricht

Non-solvent vs. vapor induced phase separation

Materials & methods

membrane casting for VIPS (green arrows) and NIPS (red arrow)

	VIPS	NIPS
structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> isotropic spongelike rough surface 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> anisotropic finger pores dense surface layer
pore characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> microfiltration narrow pore size distribution porosity up to 90% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ultrafiltration porosity < 85%
pros/cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + highly hydrophobic - more difficult processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + simple set-up + well established - limited porosity

• PVDF/DMSO solution stirred over night at const. temp.

• VIPS & NIPS casting done at set conditions

- relative humidity (NIPS < 30%)
- casting thickness
- exposure time
- casting speed
- temperature
- air flow velocity

• characterization

- SEM
- porosity
- perm porometry
- thickness
- gas permeability
- contact angle

Results

SEM images of membranes casted by the NIPS and VIPS method with short and long exposure time; contact angle measurements for no, short and long exposure time to humid air

Frequency of pore size distribution

Porosity and thickness

Pore size and exposure time

Conclusion

- VIPS is a promising method for preparation of **highly porous** and isotropic membranes in the range of **microfiltration**
- Only 1 min of VIPS changes membrane structure drastically
- Pore size distribution for VIPS membranes is more narrow for long exposure time
- Even though the porosity is similar for NIPS and VIPS, VIPS membranes show much higher flux due to changes in membrane structure (finger like -> sponge like)

Outlook

- Parameters for the VIPS process need to be further explored in order to adjust certain specific membrane characteristics
- For even higher hydrophobicity membranes which can withstand plasma post treatment are of interest

Contact

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